

THE IMPACT OF VISUAL AIDS IN TEACHING AND LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: Visual aids are very effective teaching tools that can be used by teachers to help students learn a foreign language. The advantage of applying visuals in teaching are enormous from catching students' attention to encouraging them to keep up with lecture's specific topic. In this article, the use of visual aids in learning English language is examined in both theoretical and practical ways. In addition, some activities related to visual aids are suggested.

Key words: visuals, multimedia projector, photographs, Venn Diagram method, gestures, target language

Education is the most integral part of human beings as no one can succeed without vitally imperative knowledge in every sphere of the life. Education improves people's critical thinking skills like problem-solving, decision-making. It makes you more open-minded towards people. By being educated, you have better chances for your future career and it provides you with great skills to succeed. Teaching and learning are two main steps in the process of education. Teachers use variety range of methods so as to make learning effective. In the past, the most common method of teaching was lecture where the teacher was the controller of the class and students would sit in silence and had no right to ask something during the lesson. Unlike the past education, now traditional teaching methods have changed to progressive ones which include interesting activities, explaining lesson with additional visual aids such as videos, images to make lesson understandable for students. They altered the way people think about lessons when they tend to consider

classrooms like a prison. Visual aids have so much power to improve the interest in learning and it helps teachers to distribute conception easily. They are additional equipments that make lesson clearer to understand. They can be very enjoyable for students since it stimulates their interest in target language. Multiple kinds of visual aids that teachers integrate into teaching process facilitate students to gain real-life language. One of the useful sides of visuals is that they can be used for different levels in language learning. So what exactly are the visual aids? According to Gini Beqiri, “visual aids are items of a visual manner, such as graphs, photographs, video clips used in addition to spoken information”. Twinkl states that “visual aids are cues which highlight information or break something down into simple steps that we can see”. In short, they are the tools which are used in teaching and learning process to make lesson easier to understand. Thomas, M and Keinders think that applying visuals into teaching process “help the teacher to clarify, establish, correlate and coordinate accurate concepts, interpretations and appreciations, and enable him to make learning more concrete, effective, interesting, inspirational, meaningful and vivid. Some scientists such as Moriarty was in the opinion of “the need of pictorial information rather than textual among young students”. Unlike him, Paivio stated that “cognitive growth is stimulated by the balance between verbal and visual experiences in the early stages of learning”. Most of the teachers agree that visual aids help students’ motivation, interest on the given topic.

There are several types of visual aids. They are often on the form of videos, pictures, graph and charts, posters and overhead projectors. Also televisions and Internet are important for video visuals while textbooks provide wide range of pictures. Here are given extended information for some of the visuals

Videos in language learning. The use of videos for educational purposes began long ago, in early 1980s. After some years, more teachers started to integrate videos into lessons. Educators found have found movies and clips to be useful for relaying some kind of data inside the classroom since “videos enclose visual hints such as gestures and expression that are considered as a guidance for learners to go beyond of what they are listening in order to infer video’s content” as Adambayeva F said. Combining the video material into learning foreign language process allows students to guess the information through video’s

content as well as to enhance their critical thinking and awareness. Samir M.Rammal said that, “ Video has been proved to be effective method in teaching English as a foreign/second language foreign or both young”. Videos in teaching and learning language can easily introduce target culture to the students They have many prospects to be applied to improve the obtaining of listening skills. Therefore, they can show how to use and pronounce new words in real conversations as the situations in videos are very similar to those in real life such as the choice of words and the tone of the voice . Besides, they present more cultural factors of the language which might be an effective beginning to inquire into target traditions. Similarly, Sayed Mustafa Zemary mentions some useful effects of videos in learning language. First, “through videos, learners may compare and contrast societal and cultural values of their home language and target language. He also said that “the sociolinguistic markers available from context help learners relate tem to familiar experiences within their native language”. By integrating videos into English learning, teachers make students decipher the correct meaning of the context without any drawbacks. In addition, their writing skill can be also developed by looking at the subtitles of the video. They assess students obtain the correct spelling of the new learnt words. There are many activities to do with videos.

1. Vocabulary matching. Students should match the new words that they came across while watching videos with the pictures in this activity.
2. Brainstorming. Teacher gives one problem related to the video for each group and told them to give some possible solutions.
3. Discussing titles. Before watching the video students try to guess what the video is about by examining the title.

Pictures in language learning. According to Sinclair, "a picture is defined as a visual representation or image that is painted, drawn, or photographed, and rendered on a flat surface". Vast majority of educators now use pictures as an important tool to teach students. Surely, the main benefit of pictures is that they are visible to people. They lead to encourage the interest of learners to obtain foreign language. As Moore says, "students' imagination can also be inspired". For instance, the pictures with vivid colors can alter the whole vibe of the classroom as they attract student's attention. Images are an effective

way of introducing new vocabulary as they support the progress of academic and social vocabulary. It has also been suggested that pictures help teachers influence situations and inquire authenticity into language learning atmosphere. According to Rossita, Derwing, and Jones, "pictures are helpful for data collection and in analyzing learner's speech since visuals enable learners to elaborate on their both spoken and written speech". Description is one of the commonly used activities with pictures. Once a learner sees the picture, then he/she can talk about what is described in the picture. If they can not understand the context of the image, they try to guess possible suggestions and with that the critical thinking also improves. Images also help students to realize main points by connecting several visuals. *Venn Diagrams* method can be used in such circumstances. Learners should compare and contrast two pictures and find similarities between them. *Collage* method is a great way to make predictions. When students learn a new topic, they are challenged to connect several pictures which might relate to each other. *Storytelling* is the most common way of teaching language. The teacher shows 3 or 4 pictures from famous fairy-tales and asks students to retell the story. In short, images can assess English Language Learners to clarify meaning and promote understanding.

Projectors in language learning. Blackboards have always been used in classrooms as they provide learners with visual information. But after Multimedia Projectors were added to learning process, blackboards have lost their significance. Projectors are small machines designed to project an image onto a small screen or whiteboard Teaching languages, especially English has become easy with the help of projectors. Stair Yassir states that "a projector, image projector, or multimedia projector is an optical device that spots visual media such as images, videos, or documents onto a solid surface or a projection screen, making it works like a borderless TV". Projectors are very useful and time-saving equipment in classrooms as they contribute all kinds of visual files in minutes. Sharing materials via projector will give you larger picture than just showing them on a laptop which means they become easier to see on the eyes. The main advantage of using projectors is its space-saving size. According to Radius Research, 58% of students can not read content on a 70" panel. By applying projectors into lessons, teachers can display a large picture onto the wall so that students can easily see in the classroom.

The role of visual aids is very crucial to make lessons understandable in Foreign Language Teaching. By properly selecting and creating, visual aids can be an important supplement to teaching-learning process since they help keep students engaged in their work and motivated to learn. The integration of technology into classroom help educators to explain topics and ideas practically. Classes also become more engaging and interactive. The visual aids can develop learners' all 4 skills as well as their creativity and critical thinking. In today's cutting-edge world, knowing how to apply visual aids into lessons, how to install them to classrooms is must-have knowledge for teachers as they arouse the interest and encourage students.

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The Importance of Technology in Education

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Abstract: Education today faces many demands to ensure students to build their bright future. The research is evidence of the roles of technologies in teaching, learning and developing critical thinking and scientific analysis. As it seemed that there are many benefits of using technologies during lessons among learners as well as here some information is given about challenges of using technology in education. It is mentioned that this article's purpose is to inform you about the significant contributions that technology has made to education, including those of students, parents and teachers.

Key words: Education, technology, computer, teaching, method, skill, teachers, learn, tool, visual.

In every sphere, education is the most important one because it gives people the opportunity to find their own position in the future. So it includes some basic skills to survive in the world. These skills contain reading, writing proficiency and numeracy, as well as the ability to communicate and work with others. Education is important in every field for each type of job or career, and in many cases, education plays an essential role to make the difference between the ability to be able to perform a job and being unable to perform at all. Many people believe that education is necessary in life for basic survival skills. Eleanor Roosevelt famously said: "Education is essential to good citizenship and is important to life because it enables people to contribute to their community and their country". So now we should pay great attention to the quality of education. Therefore, technologies have changed some features of education. A Gallup study titled "Education Technology Use in Schools" found that about 65% of respondents said that they used digital teaching aids on a daily basis. With how quickly technology is advancing in education around the world, it cannot be ignored.

Also we cannot ignore the fact that technology is necessary for the development of the modern education system. The high-speed computers are being accepted in business, home and education areas. Educational standards and teaching methods started to integrate computers and technologies. Technology in the classroom of the twenty-first century allows for both student and teacher interaction during lessons. In particular, during online courses and educational activities, students can collaborate to solve difficulties. This is being a source to distance learning, learning tools and communication. To understand the importance of technology in education we should look at a huge number of schools, collages, universities and institutions which use computers or other technologies as a main source of teaching and learning. In view of the fact that the role of technology in education leads to increase the quality of studying.

Without the introduction of technology, it would not have been possible for teachers in this Covid-19 epidemic age to create effective learners at home. Technology also enables pupils to learn more efficiently by using online teaching resources. Here are mentioned some benefits of using technology in education.

Encourages an Efficient Educational System. Undoubtedly, since using of technologies in the classrooms, it promotes the overall development of students. During the lessons, teachers can use many technologies, such as computers, printers, projectors and so on, in order to make the lesson more accessible, exciting, colourful and enjoyable, and create a healthy educational environment. As a result of this, the interest and attention to the lesson would increase among students.

Provide Teachers More Resources. Educational technology includes a great deal of e-learning tools for teachers. It is easy to find any kind of e-version books with the help of the Internet. It can be the best opportunity to provide all necessary books among teachers. Teachers can effectively instruct students via video classes, and appealing infographics thanks to technology. Also, teachers can keep students interested by offering online quizzes and various courses.

Save Time and Money. The learner can spend less money on other resources because there are more study materials available by the help of e-learning technologies. Even now, many

schools place a greater emphasis on purchasing online study materials because they are less expensive and easier to store, so it does not require much time to find supplies. By using cutting-edge educational technologies that are available online for free, teachers may teach students more effectively and efficiently while saving time and money.

Better Understanding through Graphics. Through the use of video graphics, technology has reviewed the learning process and given humans the ability to comprehend concepts more quickly and retain them for a long period. The visual information system is the only thing that makes this possible. It is fact that people can understand the information more quickly by watching it rather than hearing or reading it. Students can maintain their interest in their academics while having fun and learning at the same time.

Challenges of Educational Technology. Together with other benefits of technology in education, somehow, we are facing challenges in creating modern educational technology in the schools. Spending a lot of time in front of the screen may lead to some health issues. For example, constant use of computers, tablets, and phones while studying could result in back discomfort, neck pain, blurred vision and other problems.

Teachers cannot control each student in online classes. This persuades people to cheat by luring them in. The most recent technology encourages pupils to cheat by exchanging test sheets, copying and pasting answers, and using Google to look up answers during an online test. Also, in some areas, the poor internet connection can be one of the challenges of education technology.

In the modern world, technology is necessary in every aspect of our everyday lives and connects us all. For students with special needs, technology use has been a practice for a very long time. By incorporating technology into the classroom, educators hope to bring about pedagogical change and address key problems that special needs students face. So why not use technology into teaching? That is, technology turns into an essential component of the learning experience and an important issue for educators, from the start of making the learning experience ready to the process of learning and instruction (Altun and Khurshid Ahmad, 2021). The only tool that contributes to the system`s improvement in multiple ways is technology. Technology significantly affects education, from teachers to students.

Education has become more adaptable and perceptive with the help of modern technology in teaching. Personalized learning materials, more interesting information, better visual comprehension, and chances for advanced learning have all been made possible by a variety of technology-driven educational technologies. It is the evidence of that through the use of technology, one can improve education and learning and provide new aspects of the same (Patil, 2020).

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